

AUTOMATION OF PHARMACY AND MEDICINE SEARCH SYSTEM**Abdiev Khusniddin**

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Abstract. Automation of Pharmacy and medicine search system software was developed using modern software. This software platform is a competitive system based on foreign experience. It is a software platform that helps the customer to find the medicine and pharmacies they need quickly and easily, as well as provides two-way convenience for both the buyer and the seller.

Keywords: medicine, pharmacy, automation, system, company production.

АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ПОИСКА АПТЕК И ЛЕКАРСТВ

Аннотация. Программное обеспечение для автоматизации Аптеки и системы поиска лекарств разработано с использованием современного программного обеспечения. Данная программная платформа представляет собой конкурентоспособную систему, основанную на зарубежном опыте. Это программная платформа, которая помогает покупателю быстро и легко найти нужные ему лекарства и аптеки, а также обеспечивает двустороннее удобство как для покупателя, так и для продавца.

Ключевые слова: медицина, фармация, автоматизация, система, фирменное производство.

INTRODUCTION

Pharmacy automation systems are a form of electronic processing of accounting documents and reports by a pharmacy employee along with all production at the pharmacy.

It consists of automated modules:

- Income and expenditure journal;
- Warehouse;
- Cashier;
- Sales analysis;
- References.

All services in the database management system (MOBT). This automated program allows you to control multiple users over the local area network and the Internet. The operation of the system consists of processing the product in the pharmacy warehouse and controlling the waste. Import of waste into the pharmacy warehouse by making electronic receipts, as well as import of waste in the system by checking the reports, ie in another automated pharmacy system. Release of goods from the warehouse The cost of exit from the warehouse of the pharmacy is formed at the time of write-off, or through sales in the cashier (Treasury) module can make the current state of the product analysis in the module, control the movement. The directory is updated automatically. The reference can be filled out independently. Again, the reference should hold the information. The analysis (analysis) module provides analysis of the process realized through the cash module, its diagrams, sending personal auto orders for subsequent construction

resources (processing) on a sales basis. Work was carried out in the automated system of pharmacies in the office-client mode. The organization of the work of the pharmacy is to work with large pharmaceutical medicines. It is impossible to keep track of all the information and control the pharmacy without an automated system. A professional program is reliable in doing the job. A computer program for pharmacies can work with large amounts of data. He will take full control of the matter in a timely manner and ensure that it is carried out in a timely manner. For the simplicity and convenience of the interface, the system has rich devices for information processing. The automated system helps to control the medicine in the pharmacy and control the reception at the pharmacy. Improving and simplifying the workflow of all data systems in a single program. The program, which includes the processes in the total case, is the implementation of production control in the pharmacy. The control function is performed automatically by the system. Requiring timely processing of the database for its full and proper operation.

Power from control and management programs:

Pharmacy;

Warehouse of medicines;

Trading firm;

Trading Company;

production;

Wholesale company;

Wholesale company;

Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Company;

production trading company;

Wholesale warehouse;

Wholesale Company;

Pharmaceutical Company;

and others

The screenshot displays the 'iMED Shop' interface. At the top, there is a green header with the text 'iMED Shop' and a red 'X' icon. Below the header, there are two buttons: 'Locate' and 'Login'. The main content area features a table with the following data:

ID	ProdName	ProdBrand	ProdCat	ProdQty	ProdPrice
4	Abacavir	Classic	Liquid	200	1200
5	Septolete	Foreign	Liquid	200	5600
6	Aspirin	Classic	Liquid	13	123
7	Neksiya	Neksiya	Bor	1	7600

Below the table, there is a section titled 'Your Bill' with a table:

ID	Product	Price	Quantity	Total
▶*				

To the left of the 'Your Bill' table, there are input fields for 'Product Id', 'Product Quantity', and 'Product Price', followed by a blue 'ADD TO BILL' button. To the right of the 'Your Bill' table, there is a blue 'Print' button and the word 'Amount'.

Introduces shop management and control.

a brief overview of pharmacy automation tools will be provided. The pharmacy control system can get all the necessary information. Regulation of the work process in the organization of the automated process of structured departments of pharmacies. The pharmacy program saves the entire case history after each contractor. Pharmacy work is an automated system to control the process of mutual accounting at the expense of the organization. The professional software of pharmacies handles large amounts of information easily and quickly. Information processing is carried out at the expense of a large number of useful equipment in a useful system. The pharmacy control system performs analytical work based on the data collected in the system. Customer activity or order statistics are available. The program monitors the execution deadlines of the issues.

Universal and fast computing system;

The food program is distributed according to the tasks performed in the organization of the work of the pharmacy departments;

Purchase a service that provides pharmacy control automation. Helps to work quickly and efficiently in a grouping, sorting and filtering system. Automating the organization of the work of structured departments of pharmacies allows you to fully control and equip the sales process. The information in the system can be converted to a format file. Automatic e-mail and SMS system;

Improving the professional work process for the pharmacy will lead to the growth of the company.

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